

Defining scenarios for seasonal climate over Europe

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Change Log

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v1	2023/12/31	First submission
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1. Executive summary

Work package 4 of the C3S2_370_MF contract proposes to design a new product for the interpretation of the ensemble seasonal forecasts (Task 4.1). This new product consists in clustering the members into several scenarios, corresponding to various atmospheric seasonal conditions in the range of possible outcomes. The focus is set on European climate, defined by average near-surface temperature, accumulated precipitation over the next season and the corresponding atmospheric circulation.

This deliverable is the final document for the task. It builds on the interim report of Milestone M4.1.1 delivered on 31 January 2023, and on our routine experimental production in real-time for more than a year. It is entirely focused on scenarios determined from a multi-model ensemble, for which such an approach is more relevant than for individual models, according to our forecasting experience. It discusses the methodological choices for clustering by investigating several options, and provides illustrations on several real-time cases in 2022 and 2023. The proposed product is shown to be a valuable tool in a real-time forecasting context to concisely summarize the multi-model spread to forecasters, and to highlight the regions where the seasonal forecast is more uncertain.

2. Introduction: context and motivation

The Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) provides outputs of numerical seasonal forecasts made with several global coupled climate models, which are freely accessible to users for their applications. At Météo-France, one of the main uses of C3S seasonal forecast data is the preparation of a seasonal forecast bulletin issued every month, that has a specific focus on the expected surface climate (temperature and precipitation) over Europe and the Mediterranean basin (WMO Research Area VI).

The elaboration of the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin involves a comparison of forecasts from several independent models. A figure such as Figure 1 (illustration on the DJF 2023 forecast issued November 2023) is one of the main figures that is analyzed when preparing the bulletin: it shows the probabilistic forecasts of the most-likely tercile category of temperature in several individual systems and in the official C3S multi-system. It is used as input for the qualitative seasonal outlook map designed by forecasters and illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 1 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature forecast for DJF 2023-2024 by the official C3S multi-system (top left), Météo-France, ECMWF, UKMO, DWD and CMCC systems¹.

¹ Taken from: https://climate.copernicus.eu/charts/packages/c3s_seasonal/

A common practice is to use the agreement or disagreement between models as a qualitative estimate of the uncertainty. However, it might be difficult for a human forecaster to synthesize the uncertainty in a multi-model using a figure like Figure 1. A first issue is that the ensemble members are not grouped according to how close they are, but to their originating modeling center. As a result, an anomaly that seems unlikely when considering the tercile probabilities of the individual systems might nonetheless be considered plausible once all members are pooled together. Moreover, the forecasting process involves a joint analysis of several co-varying variables (e.g. geopotential at 500 hPa for atmospheric circulation and climate variables at the surface), for which the uncertainties should also be taken into account simultaneously. This can hardly be done if the information from all the members is not “compressed” beforehand in a small number of possible outcomes.

Figure 2 - DJF 2023-2024 synthesis map of seasonal forecasts of surface temperature based on expert assessment (from Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin).

In order to overcome these issues, this deliverable introduces a new product we designed for the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletins. It consists in grouping the ensemble members from a multi-model ensemble of C3S seasonal forecast data into several competing scenarios, defined using a clustering algorithm. Our multi-model ensemble comprises all members from the EMCWF, CMCC, DWD, NCEP, UKMO and Météo-France systems. The role of the clustering algorithm is to summarize the uncertainty in the ensemble forecast by highlighting the main discrepancies between the members, irrespective of the data source. This product is routinely produced every month as part of the seasonal forecast bulletin, for experimental purposes.

After a brief overview of the data (Section 3), Section 4 describes the process of choosing a clustering methodology. Section 5 provides an illustration of the retained methodology on four operational case studies, while Section 6 shows some verification of scenario-based forecasting

strategies. Finally, Section 7 concludes on how these scenarios can and should be used in the context of real-time seasonal forecasting.

3. Data

Seasonal forecast data involved in this work is provided by C3S on the Climate Data Store (CDS). All the analyses are based on a multi-model ensemble comprising the 6 models listed in Table 1. These are the 6 models under consideration in the diagnostics of the Météo-France seasonal bulletin. This multi-model ensemble will simply be referred to as “the multi-model” in what follows. Note that this multi-model differs from the official C3S multi-system, that includes contributions from other modeling centers as well, and that briefly appears in some screenshots of C3S graphical products (Figures 1, 9, 12, 15). Both real-time forecasts and reforecasts are considered and feature a different ensemble size.

Model	CMCC	DWD	ECMWF	MF	NCEP	UKMO	Multi-model
Real-time ensemble size	50	50	51	51	52	50	304
Reforecast ensemble size	40	30	25	25	24	28	172

Table 1 - Ensemble sizes of the six selected C3S models and the corresponding multi-model.

The main variables under consideration are near-surface temperature at 2 m (T2M), precipitation (RR) and geopotential height at 500 hPa (Z500) anomalies, computed with respect to each model’s reforecast ensemble mean. The corresponding domains are the Europe domain for T2M and RR (29.5°W-40.5°E; 30.5°N-70.5°N) and the Euro-Atlantic (85.5°W-35.5°E, 27.5°N-80.5°N) or Northern Hemisphere domains for Z500 (180°W-180°E, 0°N-90°N). Two other diagnostics are also taken into account: atmospheric modes of variability and weather regimes. These diagnostics are routinely produced by the Météo-France operational code when post-processing the seasonal forecast data, but only for the ECMWF and Météo-France models.

The modes of variability are seasonal indices representing the projection of the seasonally-averaged Z500 anomaly field on predefined patterns determined from historical ERA-Interim data. There are three of them focused on the European climate: the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), the East Atlantic mode (EA) and the Scandinavian Blocking mode (SCAN). Weather regimes are categories affected to every day in every forecast member, by taking the daily anomaly field of Sea Level Pressure on the Euro-Atlantic region (85.5°W-35.5°E, 27.5°N-80.5°N) and choosing the closest-matching pattern among a set of four predefined regimes. In winter season, these regimes are NAO+, NAO-, Blocking and Atlantic Ridge. The quantity of interest regarding weather regimes is not the day-to-day category but the number of occurrence of each regime within a season of about 90 days. For more details on modes of variability, weather regimes and predefined patterns, the reader is invited to refer to Météo-France/DCSC/AVH (2017a) and Météo-France/DCSC/AVH (2017b).

4. Methodology

4.1 Preliminary considerations

Application of a clustering algorithm to our 304 multi-model ensemble members requires to make a certain number of choices, namely:

1. the variables involved in the clustering algorithm. The options that have been tested are T2M and RR over Europe, Z500 over the Euro-Atlantic region, and combinations of these
2. the specifications of the algorithm itself: type of algorithm and definition of a dissimilarity between members
3. various data pre-processing steps (e.g standardization or detrending)

These options lead to different clustering outcomes, that can be compared thanks to the metric defined in Appendix 1. This metric corresponds to the number of members that are classified in the same clusters when considering two clustering outcomes.

Sections 4.2 and 4.3 respectively address the choice of the algorithm and the choice of the variables, while we recap the retained solution in Section 4.4. However, note that no clustering option can be considered as leading to the “true” clustering of the ensemble data. Clustering is an unsupervised grouping method that shows its best potential when the data distribution exhibits a clear multimodality (i.e several “peaks” in the data), which is very seldom the case for ensemble forecasts in general (Atger, 1999). Eventually, the most relevant solution is chosen based on several practical criteria such as easiness to implement and a clear distinction between clusters, but this choice always remains partly arbitrary.

4.2 Testing clustering algorithms on 2m temperature

The initial option proposed in the intermediate milestone M4.1.1 (January 2023) was based on clustering the members according to their forecast of T2M anomaly maps over Europe. Here we discuss the various options that can be considered when sticking to this choice.

In M4.1.1, the dissimilarity between two ensemble members i and j is:

$$d_{i,j} = 1 - \text{ACC}(i,j),$$

where $\text{ACC}(i,j)$ is the Anomaly Correlation Coefficient, i.e a measure of spatial correlation between the anomaly maps of the two members. The original idea of using ACC as a measure of dissimilarity comes from a study by Nakaegawa and Kanamitsu (2006). In doing so, the priority is to group together members that have similar spatial patterns of anomalies, regardless of the intensity of the anomalies. Because d_{ij} is not a distance in the mathematical sense, this prohibits the use of some clustering algorithms, e.g k -means. For this reason, Nakaegawa and Kanamitsu (2006) and M4.1.1

use a hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, which accepts a wider range of dissimilarity metrics. M4.1.1 limits the number of clusters to two or three, which are chosen according to the largest height gap in the hierarchical clustering dendrogram. This clustering algorithm will be abbreviated HCLUST-ACC hereafter. Figure 3 summarizes the approach proposed in M4.1.1, to which the reader is invited to refer for more details.

Figure 3 - Summary of the clustering methodology used to defined scenarios in M4.1.1.

However, HCLUST-ACC method has strong implications that may be viewed as drawbacks, namely:

1. As a correlation, ACC ignores the intensity of anomalies and may group together two members that have similar patterns but clear differences in magnitude.
2. Hierarchical clustering is a “rigid” algorithm, i.e if two members get entangled in the same cluster at one step, they will remain together until the end.

For this reason, two other alternative algorithms have been considered:

- HCLUST-EUCL: the algorithm is still a hierarchical clustering with Ward linkage, but the dissimilarity between members i and j is the Euclidean distance D_{ij} between the two T2M anomaly maps. This takes into account potential differences in the intensity of anomalies.
- KMEANS-EUCL: the algorithm is a k -means algorithm, the distance between members i and j is also the Euclidean distance D_{ij} . It is the most widely used algorithm for clustering problems. k -means is initialized using the k -means++ framework to ensure robustness to the initial seeds.

The comparison of the three algorithms on our sample of seasonal reforecasts is shown in Table 2. The clustering is always performed on T2M anomaly maps, after sea grid points have been masked. Table 2 indicates the number of times two algorithms lead to the same clustering according to the metric defined in Appendix 1. The sample size for Table 2 is the full 1993-2016 reforecast period with the 12 initialization months, i.e $12 \times 24 = 288$.

The results in Table 2 suggest that the choice of the clustering algorithm only has a second-order influence on the final scenarios. This can also be noted for the 13 most recent real-time forecasts (from November 2022 to November 2023), for which the same analysis is provided in Appendix 2 (Table 6). Meanwhile, the theoretical behaviors of each algorithm are discussed in Appendix 3, and they confirm that that the HCLUST-ACC method is a relevant choice for scenarios to be used in the seasonal forecast bulletin because:

1. It does not only separate along the axis of maximum variance, contrary to k-means
2. It tends to separate positive and negative anomalies

For all these reasons, the HCLUST-ACC method already proposed in M4.1.1 is retained in what follows.

	HCLUST-ACC	HCLUST-EUCL	KMEANS-EUCL
HCLUST-ACC		270/288 (94%)	286/288 (99%)
HCLUST-EUCL			287/288 (99%)
KMEANS-EUCL			

Table 2 - Number of similar clusterings of the T2M anomaly maps of the multi-model reforecasts (1993-2016, 12 initialization months) obtained with different methods. The full sample size is 24 years x 12 months = 288 reforecasts. The multi-model reforecast ensemble size is 172.

Besides the clustering algorithm itself, other choices of data pre-processing may have a potential impact on the final scenarios extracted from the ensemble. In line with recommendations from a review of Milestone M4.1.1, several options have been investigated in Appendix 4 (e.g standardization, detrending, area-weighting, etc.). The conclusion of Appendix 4 is that these options have limited impact on the clustering outcome, which remains similar to the original method most of the time. The approach of M4.1.1 is therefore retained for its simplicity as it includes very little post-processing except masking of sea grid points.

4.3 Including precipitation and atmospheric circulation

4.3.1 Precipitation

The purpose of the scenario product is to provide a description of the possible climate outcomes that is consistent across the meteorological parameters of interest, e.g surface temperature and precipitation for the final communication of the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin. Therefore, this section considers three options to take precipitation into account:

1. Using the clustering previously implemented on T2M, and compositing on precipitation (M4.1.1 option). This solution has the advantage to be directly consistent between T2M and precipitation, but may not highlight the main uncertainties on precipitation.
2. Implementing another clustering on precipitation alone. This will show the strongest points of disagreement between members regarding rainfall, but may be difficult to interpret if the precipitation scenarios do not match the temperature scenarios.
3. Implementing another clustering on T2M and precipitation simultaneously.

Table 3 shows the comparisons between the three options in the reforecasts. The real-time counterpart between November 2022 and November 2023 is in Appendix 5 (Table 8). In agreement with the previous sections, clustering is the HCLUST-ACC applied to temperature or precipitation anomalies over Europe on land grid points. The combined T2M+RR clustering is performed by appending the T2M and RR anomaly maps, after normalizing by their total variance across the ensemble.

	T2M	RR	T2M+RR
T2M		134/288 (46%)	280/288 (97%)
RR			213/288 (74%)
T2M+RR			

Table 3 - Number of similar clusterings of the multi-model reforecasts (1993-2016, 12 initialization months) obtained with different sets of variables: T2M anomalies alone, RR anomalies alone and T2M+RR anomalies combined. The full sample size is 24 years x 12 months = 288 reforecasts. The multi-model reforecast ensemble size is 172.

The first result from Tables 3 and 8 is that clustering on RR leads to very different scenarios compared to T2M, with less than half of the (re)forecasts being clustered the same way. The other result is that a clustering combining T2M and RR together almost always leads to scenarios that are the same as with T2M alone. In other words, scenarios on T2M+RR are actually highlighting the discrepancies in T2M. A visual inspection of real-time cases (not shown) provides a plausible explanation for this: T2M anomalies consist in patches of positive or negative anomalies over large areas, while RR anomalies exhibit more spatial noise. This reduces their influence in the computation of ACC that defines dissimilarity between members.

4.3.2 Atmospheric circulation

The possibility to include precipitation in the scenarios also raises the question to directly take into consideration the atmospheric circulation, and not only its surface impacts. In this section, atmospheric circulation is described in terms of Z500 anomalies over the Euro-Atlantic domain (85.5°W-35.5°E, 27.5°N-80.5°N). The Euro-Atlantic domain is larger than Europe and also encompasses the North Atlantic, a large part of Greenland and the North American east coast. The choice of this domain is consistent with the definition of modes of variability and weather regimes that is used in operational seasonal forecasting at Météo-France (see Section 3).

	T2M	RR	Z500	T2M+Z500	RR+Z500	T2M+RR+Z500
T2M		134/288 (46%)	166/288 (58%)	280/288 (97%)	180/288 (62%)	259/280 (90%)
RR			231/288 (80%)	211/288 (73%)	263/288 (91%)	237/288 (82%)
Z500				228/288 (79%)	272/288 (94%)	242/288 (84%)

Table 4 - Number of similar clusterings of the multi-model reforecasts (1993-2016, 12 initialization months) obtained with different sets of variables: T2M anomalies alone, RR anomalies alone, Z500 anomalies alone and combinations involving Z500. The full sample size is 24 years x 12 months = 288 reforecasts. The multi-model reforecast ensemble size is 172.

Table 4 summarizes some comparisons of the previously tested reforecast scenarios on T2M and RR with new scenarios including Z500 data on the Euro-Atlantic domain. The real-time counterpart of Table 4 is in Appendix 5 (Table 9). The main conclusions from Tables 4 and 9 are the following:

1. Two groups of variables can be identified in terms of scenarios they define: RR and Z500 on one side, T2M on the other. This can be seen by comparing the scenarios on individual variables but also with the RR+Z500 combination, which leads to results that are similar to both RR and Z500 alone.
2. Whenever T2M is included in the combination, it tends to drive the definition of scenarios. This was true for T2M+RR in Table 3, and it can still be noted with T2M+Z500 (which produces scenarios similar to those with T2M but different from those with Z500).

Note that further investigation (not shown) has also highlighted a slight seasonal dependency regarding T2M vs Z500 clusters: these two sets of clusters are more consistent for initializations in extended boreal winter (NDJFMA) than initializations in extended boreal summer (MJJASO).

4.4 Retained solution

Results from Sections 4.2 and 4.3 suggest that two options of clustering variables can be retained: T2M alone, or RR+Z500 combined together. Most of the following results will focus on the T2M scenarios, which have been more extensively analyzed in our real-time experimentation. Scenarios on precipitation and Z500 are therefore represented as composites on the T2M clusters. Although this is not always optimal to separate the members according to their precipitation or atmospheric circulation, compositing ensures consistency of the scenarios across all variables. Also note that in many forecasts, the T2M clusters prove to be easy to interpret in terms of Z500 and precipitation patterns, while the RR+Z500 clusters provided less insight regarding temperature spread across members.

As for the technical details, the final choice is the same as M4.1.1, applied to our multi-model combination of six C3S models:

- The clustering algorithm is HCLUST-ACC
- Only 2 or 3 clusters are allowed to make the forecasters' task easier. The optimal number is based on the largest merging distance on the dendrogram.
- T2M and RR anomalies are considered over the European domain (29.5°W-40.5°E; 30.5°N-70.5°N), with sea grid points masked. They are neither standardized nor detrended, and are not area-weighted.
- Z500 anomalies are considered on the Euro-Atlantic domain (85.5°W-35.5°E; 27.5°N-80.5°N)

5. Implementation of scenarios on case studies

5.1 Introduction to case studies

The purpose of this section is to illustrate how the scenario product is being used for the seasonal bulletin process in the course of this task. Scenarios based on the retained clustering solution (see Section 4.4) have been produced in real-time every month over more than a year, since the November 2022 forecast. They have also been produced retrospectively for older cases for a *a posteriori* analysis. Consequently, the verification ACC against the ERA5 T2M reference anomalies is displayed whenever available.

Here we describe 4 examples, showing a variety of situations forecasters can be confronted with when using this new product, and how they can take advantage of it. Moreover, this section is meant to showcase the range of diagnostic figures that have been designed to describe the scenarios and their impact.

5.2 Case 1: AMJ 2022 forecast initialized March 2022

Figure 4 - (a) AMJ 2022 synthesis map of seasonal forecasts of surface temperature based on expert assessment (from the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin issued in March 2022) (b) ERA5 verification of the tercile categories in AMJ 2022 relative to the 1993-2016 climatology.

The expert assessment of seasonal forecasts for AMJ 2022 (issued in March 2022) highlighted a warm anomaly over Western Europe (Figure 4a) which actually occurred according to the ERA5 reanalysis (Figure 4b). However, the bulletin failed to anticipate the cold and normal conditions that were experienced in Eastern and Central Europe, because the corresponding Z500 negative anomaly were not forecast either. The ACC (i.e spatial correlation) between the multi-model ensemble mean

– which forecasts warmer than normal conditions everywhere (Figure 5) – and the corresponding ERA5 anomalies is about 0.47, quantifying the fact that the forecast was partly successful.

Clustering of the multi-model leads to two scenarios. Scenario 1 exhibits warmer than normal temperatures all over Europe, similar to the ensemble mean but with stronger anomalies to the north and the east. On the contrary, Scenario 2 shows the warmest anomalies around the Mediterranean basin and normal conditions over Russia and Scandinavia. These two scenarios are evenly distributed across the multi-model ensemble with 157 and 147 members respectively. Note that Scenario 2 is eventually closer to the truth (ACC = 0.73) than Scenario 1 (ACC = 0.22).

Figure 5 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature in the AMJ 2022 forecasts by the full multi-model ensemble and by the two T2M-based scenarios.

Figure 6 - Distribution of the NAO, EA and SCAN mode indices forecast for AMJ 2022 across the ensemble members of the ECMWF and Météo-France models. Members are grouped together (in gray) or according to their corresponding T2M-based multi-model scenario (in red and blue). ERA5 verification is shown as red dots.

Further compositing analysis enables to summarize the differences in atmospheric circulation that lead to temperature differences between the two scenarios. For instance, the Scandinavian Blocking mode is a discriminant feature: it is shifted to lower and sometimes negative values in Scenario 2 (Figure 6). This is consistent with lower Z500 anomalies in the northeastern part of the domain (e.g over Scandinavia, Figure 7) leading to the lower temperatures. As far as precipitation is concerned (Figure 8), the scenario decomposition also reveals that the dry conditions around the Mediterranean that appear in the ensemble mean are mostly determined by what happens in Scenario 2. In this region, the coinciding warm and dry conditions are in agreement with the

summer temperature-precipitation relationship (i.e “warmer is drier”). These dry conditions actually occurred in AMJ 2022, initiating the long-lasting 2022 drought conditions over a large part of Europe.

Figure 7 - Composite of Z500 anomalies in AMJ 2022 in the full multi-model ensemble and in the two T2M-based scenarios.

Figure 8 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of precipitation in the AMJ 2022 forecasts by the full multi-model ensemble and by the two T2M-based scenarios.

Figure 9 shows the set of figures that were used in real-time for the preparation of the bulletin. They correspond to the probabilities of the most likely tercile category in five C3S models and in the multi-system. With such a visualization, the normal temperatures in the northeastern part of the domain – revealed by Scenario 2 – are only suggested by the ECMWF and CMCC models. Scenarios could therefore have been used as a complement to identify the regions where the temperature

anomalies are more uncertain. Had they been available at that time, they would have suggested slight changes in the synthesis map compared to that of Figure 4a, with an extension of the warm anomaly to the British Isles (visible in both scenarios) and a reduction of its extent in the northeast.

Figure 9 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature forecast for AMJ 2022 by the official C3S multi-system (top left), Météo-France, ECMWF, UKMO, DWD and CMCC systems.

5.3 Case 2: SON 2022 forecast initialized August 2022

Figure 10 - (a) SON 2022 synthesis map of seasonal forecasts of surface temperature based on expert assessment (from the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin issued in August 2022) (b) ERA5 verification of the tercile categories in SON 2022 relative to the 1993-2016 climatology.

In Autumn 2022, Western Europe and the Mediterranean basin also experienced warmer than normal temperatures (Figure 10b) that were correctly anticipated in the expert bulletin (Figure 10a), but the warm anomalies did not extend to northeast Europe as anticipated. Our multi-model ensemble mean suggests uniform warm anomalies over Europe, but these anomalies do not exceed 1°C (Figure 11, light orange color). This leads to a reasonable forecast performance which is only lessened by the failure to predict the normal conditions in northeast Europe. The resulting ACC is 0.72.

Figure 11 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature in the SON 2022 forecasts by the full multi-model ensemble and by the two T2M-based scenarios.

The first scenario holds a strong majority (240 members out of 304) and is very similar to the ensemble mean, with even warmer anomalies on the Eastern half of the domain. The second scenario proposes a minority alternative (64 members) with a dipole of warm anomalies to the West and cold anomalies to the East. Compared to the ensemble mean, none of the scenarios is actually closer to the actual outcome: the best scenario is Scenario 1, with an ACC of 0.64 which is less than that of the ensemble mean. However, a consideration of the disagreement between scenarios (not available at that time either) about the anomalies in northeastern Europe might have helped reduce the extent of the warm anomalies in the expert forecast of Figure 10a. Such adjustment of the forecast was less evident if considering only the individual models from Figure 12.

Figure 12 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature forecast for SON 2022 by the official C3S multi-system (top left), Météo-France, ECMWF, UKMO, DWD and CMCC systems.

5.4 Case 3: JJA 2023 forecast initialized May 2023

Figure 13 - (a) JJA 2023 synthesis map of seasonal forecasts of surface temperature based on expert assessment (from the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin issued in May 2023) (b) ERA5 verification of the tercile categories in JJA 2023 relative to the 1993-2016 climatology.

The expert seasonal forecast for summer 2023 anticipated warmer than normal conditions over Western Europe, Central Europe and the Mediterranean (Figure 13a). On the contrary, no forecast was proposed for Eastern and Northern Europe. This can be related to the two scenarios of the multi-model forecast (Figure 14), where the minority Scenario 2 (only ~ 20% of the ensemble, 64

members) delivers a different message from the ensemble mean, with normal conditions all over Scandinavia, Western Russia and Central Europe.

When confronted to the observations, this expert forecast was globally correct, although a bit conservative as the warm anomalies actually extended further to the east and the north, e.g over Scandinavia (Figure 13b). Nonetheless, the normal temperatures that were actually experienced over Western Russia tend to prove that the members in Scenario 2 had captured the main gradient of temperature across the European continent, even though it was slightly shifted. The forecasts from the individual models in Figure 14 suggest that this gradient could mostly be noted in ECMWF and Météo-France models, but in that case the scenario product is a more condensed way to visualize it.

Figure 14 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature in the JJA 2023 forecasts by the full multi-model ensemble and by the two T2M-based scenarios.

When it comes to verification against the actual ERA5 anomalies, the ACC suggests that the ensemble mean was finally closer to the truth than any of the two scenarios, because Scenario 1 is showing very warm conditions in Western Russia where they were normal, while Scenario 2 has a warm-normal limit that is too strongly shifted to the west.

Figure 15 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature forecast for JJA 2023 by the official C3S multi-system (top left), Météo-France, ECMWF, UKMO, DWD and CMCC systems.

5.5 Case 4: DJF 2023-2024 forecast initialized November 2023

Figure 16 - (a) DJF 2023-2024 synthesis map of seasonal forecasts of surface temperature based on expert assessment (from the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin issued in November 2023)

This last case has already been touched upon in the Introduction (Figures 1 and 2) and is a real-time case at the time of writing, so verification is unknown. The expert forecast in Figure 16a suggests warmer than normal conditions over most Europe, with an increase in probability as we get closer to the Mediterranean. This is consistent with the scenario product that was used to design the synthesis map (Figure 17): while the majority scenario is anticipating warm temperatures everywhere and drives the ensemble mean owing to its strong weight (about 80% of members), the main point of disagreement among members is related to the temperatures over Northern Europe. Indeed, they are colder than normal in the minority Scenario 2, hence the absence of forecast anomalies over Scandinavia in Figure 16a. Note that such a disagreement among the multi-model ensemble members can hardly be detected from the individual models' forecast maps (see Figure 1).

Figure 17 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of 2m temperature in the DJF 2023-2024 forecasts by the full multi-model ensemble and by the two T2M-based scenarios.

Figure 18 - Number of days in each of the four weather regimes in the DJF 2023-2024 forecasts (colored bars) according to the ensemble members from ECMWF and Météo-France models altogether and separated according to their corresponding T2M-based multi-model scenario. The white bars in the background indicate the climatological number of days expected in DJF when combining ECMWF and MF reforecasts.

Figure 19 - Composite of Z500 anomalies in DJF 2023-2024 in the full multi-model ensemble and in the two T2M-based scenarios.

Figure 20 - Probability maps of the most likely tercile category of precipitation in the DJF 2023-2024 forecasts by the full multi-model ensemble and by the two T2M-based scenarios.

The composite analysis of the atmospheric circulation in the two scenarios suggests that their difference mostly relies in the shift from days with a NAO+ weather regime to days with a NAO- weather regime (Figure 18). This is in line with the composite anomalies of geopotential at 500 hPa (Figure 19), which reveal that the midlatitude storm track is shifted to the south in Scenario 2 compared to Scenario 1. Another consequence is the strong difference between the scenarios in terms of precipitation, even though they are based on a temperature clustering. As for precipitation (Figure 20), the large-scale conditions seem to be favorable to wetter than normal conditions over Europe as illustrated by the ensemble mean, but there are regional discrepancies highlighted by the

scenarios. For instance, Scenario 2 shows a strong north-south dipole of precipitation anomalies, with a wetter Mediterranean and a drier Scandinavia. This is in good agreement with the expected temperature-precipitation relationship in winter season: colder is drier, while wetter is warmer.

6. Do scenarios verify better than the ensemble mean?

This section focuses briefly on what would happen in terms of skill if forecasts only consisted in one scenario instead of the full ensemble. This is equivalent to subsampling the ensemble members, as proposed by other works such as Dobrynin et al (2018). The notable difference with these works is that the criterion to select the members is not based on agreement with a statistical model, but on their difference from the other members of the ensemble. Although such a subsampling approach is not the purpose of the scenario product for real-time forecasting, it is nonetheless interesting for *a posteriori* analysis of the members that capture the right or wrong signals.

Two scenario forecasting strategies are considered in the following analysis:

1. Forecasting the majority scenario
2. Forecasting the scenario which has the highest forecast performance in terms of ACC

Obviously, the second option is not applicable in real-time and can only be implemented in a process such as the Météo-France seasonal verification bulletin, issued when observations are available. It has also been considered in another work on member clustering of short-range forecasts by Lamberson et al (2023).

Figure 21 - Distribution of the Anomaly Correlation Coefficient (ACC) of the multi-model seasonal reforecasts over Europe against ERA5 for all initializations in 1993-2016 (sample size 12 x 24 = 288). Blue curve: Multi-model ensemble mean (all 172 members). Red curve: Scenario with highest ACC among scenarios. Green curve: Majority scenario.

Figure 21 shows the distributions of the T2M ACC forecast skill for the multi-model across the 1993-2016 reforecast period, i.e with only 172 members available. One of them corresponds to the ACC of the ensemble mean, while the other two are representing the two forecasting strategies described above. Unsurprisingly, the red curve shows that forecast performance would be better if we could choose in advance the scenario that is closer to the truth: the distributions are shifted to higher ACC values. On the contrary, forecasting the majority scenario, which is doable in real-time, leads to a distribution of ACCs that is more spread out. On the one hand, it may lead to a higher ACC by removing some irrelevant minority scenario. But on the other hand, it may degrade the forecast by increasing its sharpness at locations where most members actually get the wrong signal. Such a situation was illustrated in Section 5 with three of the case studies (AMJ 2022, SON 2022 and JJA 2023). The largest extension of the ACC distribution to the lower than to the upper tail even suggests that degradation is the most likely option. Consequently, in the absence of additional knowledge, forecasting the majority scenario is a risky choice that should not be preferred to forecasting the ensemble mean.

Figure 22 - Anomaly Correlation Coefficient (ACC) of recent multi-model real-time forecasts. Blue curve: Full ensemble mean (304 members). Red curve: Scenario with highest ACC among scenarios. The number of members in the majority scenario is indicated by the gray bars, and the number of scenarios appears at the bottom of the bars.

Figure 22 proposes to enrich the analysis to the most recent multi-model real-time forecasts for which verification is available. The blue dots indicate the ACC of the multi-model ensemble mean (304 members) on the left axis, while the red dots indicate the ACC of the scenario that has the highest ACC, that is to say in “perfect” mode. In order to know whether this “best” scenario is a majority or a minority scenario, the grey bars indicate its number of members on the right axis. In these last 16 cases, the benefits of a “best” scenario – compared to the ensemble mean – are less evident than in the previous Figure 22. In most cases, the “best” scenario is the majority scenario. However, it does not necessarily prove better than the ensemble mean, and can even be worse (e.g

the August 2022 forecast from Section 5.3). Among those cases, the only one that actually stands out is the March 2022 forecast from Section 5.2, for which one of the scenarios clearly outperforms the ensemble mean. This can be linked to the fact it is also the only forecast with evenly populated scenarios.

7. Conclusion

This deliverable has explored several clustering methodologies to define scenarios for European climate over the next season in an ensemble seasonal forecast. These methodologies were applied to a multi-model ensemble, grouping together the C3S forecasts provided by CMCC, DWD, ECMWF, Météo-France, NCEP and UKMO. Various options were considered to assess the impact of the clustering algorithm, the impact of the variables involved in the clustering and the impact of pre-processing steps such as standardization or detrending. Unsurprisingly, the choice that has the most notable impact is the climate variables involved, with strong differences between clustering methods taking 2m temperature into account and those based only on precipitation and/or Z500. In order to remain consistent with our current pre-operational practice and the previous work from Milestone M4.1.1, the scenario product illustrated on four case studies is the one based on 2m temperature. The case studies are also completed with a more systematic assessment of forecast performance when assuming subsampling strategies with only one scenario retained.

Based on these investigations and a review of the pre-operational product with forecasters from the Météo-France climate services department, the main benefits of using scenarios in real-time seasonal forecasting are the following:

1. Scenarios provide a condensed yet precise representation of the multi-model ensemble spread. The differences between the scenarios and the member populations form an indication of whether the ensemble is tight or spread out.
2. The similarities and differences between scenarios reveal where the seasonal forecast is more confident, and where it is more uncertain. This is greatly valuable for the preparation of expert forecasts such as synthesis maps.
3. Scenarios help forecasters interpret at one glance the signals that appear in the full ensemble, preserving consistency across variables. For instance, whenever there is weak or no signal, scenarios enable to know whether it is due to a large spread – with both positive and negative anomalies in the ensemble – or to all members forecasting values that are close to climatology.

These three points suggest that scenarios applied to a multi-model of C3S forecast data are a relevant complement or alternative to the comparison of the individual models' forecasts when preparing the seasonal forecast bulletin.

However, beyond this specific context, it is misleading to consider scenarios as a tool to improve average skill scores by selecting one presumably “best” scenario. Retaining one scenario leads to exacerbate the forecast in one specific direction and make it overconfident. For instance, when it comes to ACC, the forecast will be more heavily penalized if it predicts an anomaly opposite to the outcome than if it predicts a near-zero anomaly. As a result, there is no point in relying only on a majority scenario, which is likely less skillful than the full ensemble: the set of scenarios should be considered together.

This deliverable finishes Task 4.1 of the C3S2_370_MF contract, but developments on scenarios for the Météo-France seasonal forecast bulletin are planned to continue. First, the product on

temperature will still be issued every month for internal use. In the future, it may also be implemented with the rest of the graphical production for the Météo-France seasonal prediction website, depending on uptake. In the meantime, the comparison between scenarios obtained from temperature and those obtained from another relevantly chosen set of variables (i.e Z500 and/or precipitation) will be carried out more systematically during the elaboration of each operational seasonal forecast bulletin, in order to determine the most relevant use of these two competing products.

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Appendix 1: How similar are two clustering methods?

Let’s assume that we have two clustering methods A and B that are applied to the same real-time seasonal forecast consisting in 304 members. Let’s also assume they lead to the same number of clusters k (typically, $k = 2$ or 3). The question is to know whether clustering methods A and B have led to the same scenarios for the seasonal forecast under consideration.

The contingency table, as illustrated by the example in Table 5a, indicates how the members are jointly classified methods A and B. To quantify how similar the two clustering outcomes are, the metric is simply the number of members that are classified in the “same” cluster with both methods. Obviously, this cannot be done by direct use of the clusters’ numbering (Cluster 1, Cluster 2, etc.) because they may differ from one clustering to another. The counting is actually done recursively:

1. the highest value in the contingency table (e.g 98 in Table 5a) corresponds to members classified in the same cluster (e.g in Table 5a, Cluster 1 from method A identifies to Cluster 2 from method B).
2. the corresponding row and column are “removed” from the contingency table (see Table 5b)

Steps 1 and 2 are repeated until no values are left in the contingency table. For instance, in Table 5b, Cluster 3 from method A is identified to Cluster 1 from method B, then row 3 and column 1 will be removed as well. The number of members that are clustered the same by both methods is the sum of the maxima identified at all repetitions of Step 1. In the example, the value is 152 members (98 + 54 + 0).

Table 5a				Table 5b			
	Method B				Method B		
Method A	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Method A	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Cluster 1	42	98	0	Cluster 1			
Cluster 2	35	40	0	Cluster 2	35		0
Cluster 3	54	0	35	Cluster 3	54		35

Table 5 - Counting the number of members classified in the same clusters with method A and method B. See text for details.

However, the number of members found with this counting cannot indicate alone if methods A and B have led to a similar clustering. Indeed, this number is linked to the total number of members, as well as the proportions of members in each cluster. In order to find a threshold for similarity between the two clustering methods, we count the number of members that get classified into the same groups when two independent random groupings are made. An additional condition is that one grouping must have the same proportions as method A, while the other must have the same proportions as method B. The distribution of this number of members randomly classified the same is sampled by repeating the random draws 1,000 times, and the threshold is defined as the 95th percentile. In other words, method A and method B are considered to provide the same clustering

outcome if the number of members classified similarly – according to the counting described in Tables 5a and 5b – has less than 5% probability to occur by chance.

Appendix 2: Comparison of clustering algorithms on real-time forecasts

	HCLUST-ACC	HCLUST-EUCL	KMEANS-EUCL
HCLUST-ACC		10/13 (77%)	13/13 (100%)
HCLUST-EUCL			13/13 (100%)
KMEANS-EUCL			

Table 6 - Same as Table 2 for the multi-model real-time forecasts from November 2022 to November 2023. The full sample size is 13 forecasts. The multi-model real-time ensemble size is 304, note that it differs from the reforecast ensemble size in Table 2 (172).

Appendix 3: Theoretical comparison of algorithms

A simplified two-dimensional illustration of the principles behind the three algorithms HCLUST-ACC, HCLUST-EUCL and KMEANS-EUCL is shown in Figure 23. The top row corresponds to the T2M anomalies at two randomly chosen grid points in Europe in the 304 ensemble members of the DJF 2023-2024 multi-model forecast. The bottom row corresponds to synthetic data generated by 10,000 random draws from a bivariate Gaussian distribution. This bivariate distribution has the same means and covariance matrix as the T2M anomalies on the first row. The number of clusters is set to $k=2$, which is the optimal number of clusters determined from the dendrogram for HCLUST methods. This data is quite representative of what is happening in higher dimension if the forecast distribution can be considered unimodal.

Figure 23 - Illustration of the three clustering algorithms KMEANS-EUCL, HCLUST-EUCL and HCLUST-ACC on bidimensional data. Top row: DJF 2023-2024 T2M anomalies in the multi-model forecast at 2 random grid points. Bottom row: synthetic bivariate Gaussian random data.

The toy random data in the bottom row enables to visualize more easily the behavior of the three clustering algorithms:

1. The KMEANS-EUCL separates between both sides of the ensemble mean along the axis of maximum variance. It leads to evenly populated clusters and overlooks the secondary axes of dispersion.
2. The HCLUST-EUCL method separates the clusters by taking an irregular “contour” around which data points are the most sparse.

3. The HCLUST-ACC method separates the clusters along two rays starting from the origin of the phase space (i.e zero anomaly), around which data points are the most sparse. It will tend to separate the clusters into positive vs negative anomalies.

The comparison between the two rows also shows that, although the clustering methods theoretically lead to very different solutions (bottom row), the results on a finite ensemble where data is sparse (top row) can be more similar.

Appendix 4: Impact of data pre-processing options

Assuming the HCLUST-ACC clustering algorithm applied to T2M anomalies, several choices of data pre-processing may influence the seasonal forecast scenarios. Some of these choices were pointed by a previous review of this work, following Milestone M4.1.1. The investigated options are listed below.

- 1. Standardization of the T2M anomalies at each grid point.** In Section 4.2, T2M anomalies correspond to the raw (i.e. unstandardized) difference between T2M of a given forecast, and the average T2M over the full reforecast of the same initialization month. However, the absolute year-to-year variability of temperature in °C is stronger in some parts of Europe (e.g. Scandinavia and Eastern Europe) than in others (e.g. Iberian peninsula). As this variability also influences the ensemble dispersion, a clustering on unstandardized anomalies may give more weight to locations where the year-to-year variability is stronger, such as Scandinavia. In order to remove this effect, the T2M anomalies at each grid point can be standardized with the standard deviation over the reforecast period for the same initialization month.
- 2. Area-weighting of grid point anomalies.** In order to give more weight to grid points covering a larger area, T2M anomalies at each grid point can be multiplied by the area of the grid point before performing the HCLUST-ACC clustering. The area is proportional to the cosine of the latitude.
- 3. Removing the land-sea mask.** The first version in M4.1.1 was implemented on land grid points only, due to their stronger relevance to users. However, the European continent features a lot of islands or peninsulas where land grid points are surrounded by sea. It should be tested that masking sea grid points does not lessen the influence of the peninsulas on clustering, compared to the large land masses in Central and Eastern Europe.
- 4. Averaging temperatures over consistent regions before clustering.** In line with the motivation to give equitable weights to the large areas of Central Europe and to the peninsulas, an alternative data clustering is proposed. It does not use the T2M anomalies at each grid point but on larger regions aggregating several grid points together. The regions are defined thanks to another clustering, which is a spatial clustering that groups together the grid points exhibiting similar variations across the ensemble members. The T2M anomaly in each region is the average of the anomalies in its grid points. In doing so, each region has the same importance in the clustering irrespective of its size.
- 5. Linear detrending of temperature.** The climate change trend has a strong footprint on the seasonal forecasts of temperature anomalies, because the reference climatology corresponds to the 1993-2016 period and the climate has warmed since then, leading to warmer than normal anomalies for most real-time forecasts. It is therefore relevant to assess whether this impacts the clustering of members into scenarios.

Standardization	Area weighting	With sea grid points	Regional aggregation	Linear detrending
282/288 (98%)	278/288 (96%)	284/288 (99%)	282/288 (98%)	284/288 (99%)

Table 7 - Number of clusterings of the multi-model reforecasts (1993-2016, 12 initialization months) that are similar to the clustering method of M4.1.1 and Section 4.2, using various data pre-processing options. The clustering algorithm is HCLUST-ACC for all cases.

The comparison of these five alternative data pre-processing options with the original clustering approach of M4.1.1 is summarized in Table 7. The impacts of these options over 288 reforecasts appear to be limited, as they lead to similar clusters as the original method most of the time.

Appendix 5: Comparison of real-time scenarios with several variable combinations

	T2M	RR	T2M+RR
T2M		5/13 (38%)	13/13 (100%)
RR			9/13 (69%)
T2M+RR			

Table 8 - Same as Table 3 for the multi-model real-time forecasts from November 2022 to November 2023. The full sample size is 13 forecasts. The multi-model real-time ensemble size is 304, note that it differs from the reforecast ensemble size in Table 3 (172).

	T2M	RR	Z500	T2M+Z500	RR+Z500	T2M+RR+Z500
T2M		5/13 (38%)	7/13 (54%)	13/13 (100%)	6/13 (46%)	10/13 (77%)
RR			8/13 (61%)	7/13 (54%)	13/13 (100%)	11/13 (85%)
Z500				13/13 (100%)	12/13 (92%)	10/13 (77%)

Table 9 - Same as Table 4 for the multi-model real-time forecasts from November 2022 to November 2023. The full sample size is 13 forecasts. The multi-model real-time ensemble size is 304, note that it differs from the reforecast ensemble size in Table 4 (172).

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